

STUDENTS' CHALLENGES IN EMBRACING VARIOUS TEACHING STRATEGIES IN MATHEMATICS: A PHENOMENOLOGY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 6

Pages: 717-731

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2185

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13304149

Manuscript Accepted: 07-22-2024

Students' Challenges in Embracing Various Teaching Strategies in Mathematics: A Phenomenology

Maria Junavie E. Quilestino,* Edel Shae E. Atienza, Anjielyn T. Baguio, Joyce Ann B. Bornea, Clear P. Caldusa, Jey Ann M. Cortes, Jevan Rey A. Javierto, John Vincent L. Panuan, Cyril A. Cabello

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Mathematics is a complex subject where different teaching strategies need to be considered and utilized to teach more engagingly. However, each student has a different level of intellectual capacity some can learn fast, and some take time to internalize the topic. This study investigates the lived experiences of the students towards different strategies in teaching mathematics. The study used a qualitative methodology that utilizes Heideggerian Phenomenology and Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) anchored on the Modified Van Kaam Approach popularized by Moustakas. The participants in this study were chosen using purposive sampling with inclusion criteria. The researchers conducted face-to-face interviews with ten BSED-Math students who are studying at Cebu Technological University which led to the following themes (1) The Pessimist, (2) The Optimist, (3) The Self-Directed, (4) The Discomfort, and (5) The Teachers' Criticizers. These themes emphasized the experiences and the unbearable pain of the students. It is advised to take the participants' degree of intelligence into account when planning how the teacher will present the lesson and by soliciting and taking into account the students' feedback both during and after the discussion as the class as a whole will benefit from smooth learning transitions.

Keywords: *students' challenges, Heideggerian phenomenology, lived experiences, teaching strategies, mathematics*

Introduction

Different strategies in Mathematics leave a part of the students' transformation in their field of internalizing a certain topic as Mathematics is a word that strikes fear in the mind of many students. Teachers should have considered and internalized the use of a positive learning environment and the use of teaching methods to foster various learning styles (Schulze & Bosman, 2018). According to Popova et al. (2022), a lot of teachers from remote countries struggle to achieve an effective teaching style due to a lack of skills, for which the government used the method of Professional Development Programs (PD) to improve various types of strategies to enhance teacher's competency. As Mathematics is a complex subject that involves solving problems and different equations, effective strategies should be incorporated to prevent confusion among students, making it more difficult for them to understand (Bacong et al., 2023). Students' different burdens towards math subjects are valid, especially when they feel the pressure, stress, confusion, and worst, emotional breakdowns. With this, the researchers were prompted to seek students' challenges towards the different strategies in teaching mathematics. Implementation of educational programs at the university is salient which aim to understand the class dynamics that encourage learners to feel motivated to learn and drawn lesser with the stressor that creates barrier in their learning process (Trigueros et al., 2020).

Math stress is a universal educational issue that requires full attention from both researchers and educators that will help students attain their full academic potential (Ramirez et al., 2018). Student's math stress happened when they couldn't get the lesson, specifically in a way where teachers are reading without hints of interactions in the class. In a scenario in which a teacher demonstrates confidence in a growth mindset by which evoking students to try activities again later after failing once, students reported feeling noticeably higher levels of stress compared to the teacher which demonstrates confidence in a set mindset stating that a few children still struggle with math (Bosch, 2022). Recent research shows that people can possess arithmetic anxiety, causing cognitive, emotive, or bodily reactions in various ways. According to Jamieson et al. (2021), dominant levels of math anxiety are linked to poorer exam results and students' perceptions of greater demand and fewer coping mechanisms. The impact on the students is directly related to the teacher's level of mathematical anxiety. When the teacher was dubious of his or her mathematical ability, performance suffered.

According to Nagro et al. (2017) improving student outcomes through effective academic instruction has always been the key. In some cases, different strategies used by teachers don't fit the learners' preference in internalizing mathematics subjects. According to Hu et al. (2021) in the matter of fostering children's critical thinking, teachers are unproductive when setting and questioning students' responses and actions. But there has always been a solution to every problem and for students who had trouble in dealing math subjects or experienced stress when attempting to solve math-related problems, there are always solutions for that. According to Fajriah (2017), to enhance their instructional practices, teachers must know their students' perspectives and analyze the student's needs in such a way that they can change their teaching methods and their attitudes. Researchers wanted to figure out the stress and pain of every student who is facing it and to identify how to deal with these situations. According to Seiter (2017), ineffective teaching strategies create math phobia to students which leads to their lack of success in achieving a good mathematical mindset. She also stated that to be an effective teacher, one must know how to teach mathematics using the principles and the Before, During, and After Lesson Plan format because this will lessen the anxiety of the students.

Students have their preferences towards mathematics as a subject. According to Mazana et al. (2019) numerous variables, involving

students' interest and viewpoint of the subjects, teacher's strategies, and the academic setting, bring forth an impact on how competently students grasp and thrive in mathematics. This indicates that ineffective learning and assessment strategies, institutional resources, failure to comprehend instructions, and instructor didactic strategies are all factors in the failure to learn. Thus, these matters should be given attention as these will affect their learning and academic performance. When the teacher had the chance to identify students' academic challenges, it would motivate them to modify and enhance their teaching methods such as calculating gamified elements to cater to the needs of the students wherein the latter could get different takeaways from the subject (Cabello et al., 2021). Furthermore, with the proposed actions, students would be motivated to learn despite their different styles of internalizing the specific concepts of a certain math topic. Considering Flipped Classroom as an innovative strategy for teachers in the delivery of lessons will lead students to improve their potential and skills in learning mathematics, despite having a bit of difficulties in the teaching process, nevertheless, it provides a great opportunity for students to enhance their mathematical skills and thus teachers' can make a change by enhancing students' potential through flipped classroom approach of teaching (Cevikbas & Kaiser, 20).

Literature Review

In the traditional learning approach, students struggle mostly in math subjects. Hence, the teaching strategies of the teachers matter, including their ways of delivering the discussion. Teachers are the mentors inside the classroom and students learn from them. Thus, the learnings of the students rely on the teachers, most likely on how they are going to teach and handle the students, as the latter might have different levels of understanding from one another. The researchers aim to determine the unbearable pain caused by the different strategies in teaching mathematics. This portion contains the different studies that have significant relevance to the current study that the researchers are conducting. These former studies have been gathered cautiously and precisely under the applicability to this study. Through these studies, a deeper understanding could be acquired of the unbearable pain brought by the different strategies in teaching mathematics.

Learning difficulties in mathematics have been widespread and tough for everyone. Thus, effective teaching approaches matter as students are different from one another (Segarino et al., 2022). This study focuses on the strategies for improving students' learning in mathematics. The results show that students who perceive themselves positively are more likely to engage in productive learning (Cabello et al., 2023). It was recommended to offer students the proper praise at the right time, work with them to improve their problem-solving skills, give them the chance to showcase their talents and skills, supervise their learning habits, and allow them to understand their success and failure. These approaches can be implemented by the teachers in their classrooms particularly if their students are struggling in learning mathematics (Khanal, 2022).

The impact of flipped modality on students' attainment, the participant opinions of its advantages, and its primary difficulties in implementing flipped learning. The flipped classroom outperformed its regular classroom in delivering its regular classroom for the delivery of the lesson properly, by not acquiring any evidence of public bias. Furthermore, they conducted the synthesizing of their research with an additional sixty-one studies that showed flipped classroom strategy improvement where students learn in three key areas: extending class schedule for the task and practices, gaining new knowledge with pre-existing beliefs and real and automatic feedback (Lo et al., 2017). In a flipped classroom, the instructor prioritizes resources for students to study in advance to avoid uncertainties that might lead them bombarded by thoughts of fear and anxiety when engaging with the subject. This teaching approach encourages students to actively engage in the study of mathematics while reducing their unfavorable opinion of the subject's difficulty.

Traditional teaching methods and curriculum, such as timed tests and material difficulty, are some direct factors that can cause math anxiety (Furner, 2017). According to Wu (2020), math anxiety is a serious type of catastrophe for every student. It is necessary to address a student's math anxiety for them to build confidence and gain interest in the subject. This example predicts that students who are unable to perform well and focus on learning math and solving problems will become nervous when called out of luck. Indirect factors similarly as inquiring questions to answer in a general manner cause students discomfort from their peers, especially when they are ill-prepared for the questions (Furner, 2017). Changing resources from changing teaching methods into a cooperative and interactive way is necessary to help the student cope with their math anxiety. This instance emphasizes the fact of the challenges of the students as it triggers their ability to do well in class due to their anxiety regarding their performance in the math lesson inside the classroom.

According to Atoyebi and Atoyebi (2022), inquiry-based learning, student-centered learning, problem-based teaching, direct teaching, single instructional approach, systematic and structured approach, creative and discovery approach, inclusive instructional strategies, and problem-based teaching styles were some of the teaching strategies that were the focus of the studies. The study found a connection between students' concerns about mathematics and the strategies used to teach it. It was discovered that inquiry-based learning, problem-based learning, creative and discovery learning, inclusive instructional strategies, and student-centered teaching methods all helped students feel less anxious about studying mathematics. Based on the findings, this systematic literature review recommends that mathematics professors must establish a friendly environment so that students can discuss mathematical topics without worrying about failing, thus it helps lower their anxiety in class.

According to Arthur et al. (2022), there is a significant contribution of peer-assisted learning to the enhancement of students' perception of learning Mathematics. Students who performed low in Mathematics can be directly affected if partnered with those who performed well. It will encourage them to perform good also to be at the same level as their partners. In this way, their interest in learning has

been heightened due to the motivation from their peers. In addition, peer-assisted learning is beneficial for students with learning disabilities as it enables them to understand the concept of Mathematics through the help of their peers. Cooperative learning in this sense fills the gap of student's fear and stress towards mathematics subjects as it subdues a portion of their pain in dealing with numbers, equations, and the reality of math as well.

According to Shin et al. (2017), students with impairments often experience difficulty with mathematics topics and struggle to comprehend mathematical concept topics. With technology, researchers recommend the use of visual models to support student learning and improve the skills necessary to complete and achieve the symbolic mathematical problem (Enario et al., 2022). Additionally, because disabled students find it difficult to fit in and act as though everything is normal, they feel additional pressure to do well in class and simultaneously with math courses. Thus, the integration of visual models and instructional mathematical tools offers the possibility of enabling students to actively engage and participate in learning the activities that are connected to mathematics subject.

Representation can be used in the process of teaching mathematics. It is an element that includes signs, diagrams, objects, etc. This element is important in the teaching process as it increases the ability of the students to recognize the concepts in mathematics. It required the researchers to explore more different aspects of using representation (Mainali, 2021). With the use of representations, it will likely lessen the pain of understanding math concepts in a way that will enable the students to actually "see" and understand math further. These representations may be in the form of diagrams, graphical displays, and other manipulative materials (Bacong et al., 2023). This is a great teaching strategy, especially for visual learner students. Representations also sort out abstract concepts and ideas in learning mathematics.

Through app-based manipulatives, mobile devices offer a significant option for supporting math students. Despite the lack of study on app-based manipulatives, the growing body of literature on virtual manipulatives usually suggests that students prefer virtual manipulatives without comprehension being compromised (Bouck et al., 2017). This is a great tool to integrate into teaching strategy to inspect the level of learning and understanding of the students through online games and quizzes. Teachers can integrate this to teach new math concepts alongside some entertainment to lessen students' difficulty in learning math. This tool creates a fun time that will motivate the students to actively participate in the discussion and most likely to learn the concepts.

According to Papama et al. (2022), a cooperative teaching strategy (CTS) is an advantageous approach to learning mathematics. CTS encourages students to work together and finish the task given to them. CTS helps reduce the distress of the students in answering math problems and promotes a helping environment for the students. Through this approach, active participation can be developed as it enables the students to be eager to answer or respond as they have found support from their group members or partners. This teaching strategy can be applied by teachers towards achieving effective teaching and learning processes. Teachers can allow their students to choose whom they want to be paired with. This will enable the students to freely voice out their ideas and will not feel uneasy in cooperating as they are comfortable with their partners. This will also lighten the burden of the teachers in implementing different strategies inside the classroom.

Teacher claims that mathematics instruction can be achieved by utilizing a variety of techniques. Yet, many circumstances prevent teachers from applying it such as the imposition of duties to complete the study for the entire semester, the absence of tangible resources to be used in the delivery of the discussion, and the poor skill of some teachers (Cabello et al., 2023). The result of the study reveals that the use of innovative tools in teaching is seldom used in Arab schools. Hence, it shows the heavy burden on teachers in teaching mathematics that needs to be addressed, which will give them space in creative teaching more than focusing on a fixed mindset. This study finds that for mathematics to be understood, engaging and engaging teaching methods should be interesting and can attract student's full attention, wherein the suggested strategies are advantageous for the learning process (Algani, 2019).

Based on the various literature cited above, the researcher intends to identify the challenges of the students in learning mathematics with the different teaching strategies utilized by teachers. The results of this study could provide the basis for the teaching and learning process development intended for educators to enhance how they present mathematics classes. Additionally, this cited literature serves not only for teachers but also for administration to foster different activities, alternatives, and approaches for teachers to acquire that will fit for the student's degree of internalizing the lesson. Moreover, these literature and studies enable the ability of educators and students to bridge the gap between learning mathematics and the absence of reservations about various teaching pedagogies. With these, teaching strategies allow students to master the course materials, evaluate the knowledge they acquire, and use the information in specific situations.

Methodology

Research Design

The Heideggerian Phenomenology design is utilized in this study. Exploring and discovering the unbearable pain of the students from the strategies incorporated by the teachers in teaching mathematics is the sole purpose of this study. Furthermore, the participants' lived experiences are identified and considered throughout the study.

Participants

This study applied purposive sampling. In this study, the inclusion criteria were crafted in choosing the right participants to express their experiences towards the strategies used by their teachers in teaching Mathematics.

Inclusion Criteria

- Participants should be bona fide students of Cebu Technological University– Moalboal, Cebu.
- Participants should be taking up a Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics.
- First-year and second-year students only.

Procedure

Before conducting the interview, a letter of consent was primarily constructed and sent to the participants to obtain their approval. Arrangement of the schedule for the face-to-face interview is being done after having the approval of the participants. All the participants were guaranteed to be in campus to conduct the interview. Interviewing is a way used by the researchers in the data collection. Ethical consideration was strictly followed by the researchers in the gathering of data.

Data Analysis

Anchored from the approach modified by the Van Kaam Approach, this study utilized Moustakas' Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

Ethical Considerations

Bell and Bryman's (2007) Ten principles of ethical considerations are used in this study. In the conduct of this study, important ethical steps are observed: (1) participants of this study are uncompromised and unharmed; (2) respect to the participants is prioritized; (3) obtaining the voluntary participation among the participants; (4) encroachment of participants' privacy is prohibited; (5) gathered information from the participants are with utmost confidentiality; (6) researchers observed the anonymity of the participants; (7) deception and any form of exaggeration just to achieve the goal of this study is strictly prohibited; (8) if applicable, any partisan from different funding and monetary involvement in this study must be boldly stipulated; (9) in obtaining relevant data in this study, researcher applied values such as honesty, integrity, and transparency in interacting with their participants lastly, (10) the presentation of the details in this study made without any biases or impartiality.

Results and Discussion

After the analysis of the data gathered, the researchers conducted five important themes; Theme 1: The Pessimist, Theme 2: The Optimist, Theme 3: The Self-Directed, and Theme 4: The Discomfort, Theme 5: The Teachers' Criticizers. These five themes showcased the lived experiences of students to the different strategies used by their teachers in teaching Mathematics.

The Pessimist

People have different outlooks in life that may affect their personal well-being and social development. Pessimism is one of these outlooks that affects the mental status of a person bearing it. When a person has a pessimistic view of life, he/she will tend to think negatively in a certain situation (Emia et al., 2022). The effect of this outlook on the students is no different. As Zhang (2022) stated, students find difficulty in learning and joining activities at school when they are on the edge of losing their will due to confrontation of the adversities they experience. They feel hopelessness and would think the worst in a situation (Gabriel et al., 2022). This can be further discussed by the words of the participants.

As Participant 1 said:

"Thuna-huna nalang walay nadato sa skuyla." (I just think that there is no one that got rich through education.)

Participant 1 suggested that just thinking in a shallow mindset that there is no wealth in education is a way of easing the pain for a short period of time.

Participant 1 also stated that,

"Maghunahuna nalang walay nadato sa skuyla then iinom. But naa gihapo'y will to pursue. Ang negative attributes kay nastrength nako to push through." (I will just think that no one got rich in education, and dwell on vices to feel some relief. And still have the will and guts to pursue. That negative attributes leads me to push through.)

Participant 1 stated that one of their coping mechanisms towards their pain in math subject is just to think that no one got rich through studying.

Participant 4 remarked that,

"Makawala ug gana, din makaapekto sa self-esteem nga morag di makaya ang math din makahunahuna'g mo shift nalang." (I have

lost my interest and then it affects my self-esteem like I can't bear math, that sometimes I will think of shifting another course.)

The researcher found out from Participant 4, that it made them feel a loss of interest and even decreased the level of their self-esteem and made them think about shifting to another course.

Participant 6 explained that,

"Makadepress, makawala siya ug gana ug maka-apekto pod sa imong self-esteem. Dili man kaya nako ang math uy. Ganahan ka nga mo shift nalang kay ma-apektuhan imong competence ba, imong confidence. Murag dili na nuon ka mosamot na nuon imong dili kabalo." (It causes depression and loss of self-esteem. It also drives me to tell myself that I can't handle math and leads me to think to shift to another course because it can affect my competence and confidence. It also causes me to the extent to dwell my thought that I can really handle math.)

The researchers found out from Participant 6, that it is depressing which causes the loss of their interest and as well as their self-esteem which at the same time drives them to think that they cannot handle math well and think to shift into another course.

Participant 8 stated that,

"Kanang kuan murag kadugayan kay murag mawala akong interest sa math gane niya dili na kaayo ko ganahan mosolve ug math problems. Ing-ana. Wala nay gana." (It leads me to loss my interest in math for a quite sometimes and I hate to solve math problems.)

It was found by Participant 8, that the more the discussion gets boring the more they lose their interest in solving math problems.

The Pessimist theme emphasized the negative thoughts of the students while taking the mathematics course with lots of mathematics subjects. Some of them would lose interest and would feel depressed while being exposed to such a subject. This causes some of them to consider taking another course.

The Optimist

Optimism enables a person to think positively on any occasion although caught in a difficult situation. An optimistic person believes that opportunities will come, and things will be better as the day goes by. With an optimistic view, benefits will come including better coping mechanism skills, comfort, and persistence. In the study of Gordeeva et al. (2019), it was found that students with an optimistic view of life would most likely achieve academic excellence. This can be further discussed by the words of the participants.

Participant 9 mentioned that,

"Kuan kanang maglisod na ug time management kay imbes mag klase, klasehan ka ikaw naman noon maning kamot sa inyuha magbalik napud ka ug review kay daghan pangutana nga wala natubag mental health, usahay kay kay kanang dili jud ka kasabot ma bisan unsaon nimu ug sabot, hopeless pero makaya raman kanang muhunong lang pahuway tapos kuan." (I have a hard time managing my time because instead of having class in school, I'll be the one to take review on the discussed topics that I find difficult. Sometimes I really can't understand, my mental health is affected. I feel hopeless, but it's fine. I just take some rest and then, continue.)

It was found out from Participant 9, that they are having trouble managing the time that instead of they are being taught by the teachers they seem to be the teacher themselves as they seek and find ways to review on their own that make them feel hopeless about their learnings, but after all, if they feel tired, they just prefer to rest and then rise again.

Participant 1 explained that,

"If maelearn judt ang strategy puyde ni itudlo if ever mateacher. Din base sa ilang strategy makacomeup kog strategy which is mas sayon." (If I can just learn the strategy, it can be taught if ever I will become a teacher. Base from their strategies, I can come up with strategies that much easier.)

It was found out that the strategy being learned can be used also when one becomes a teacher someday. Not just that, from the strategy being utilized by the teacher, the students can formulate new strategies based on it which they think is much easier for them.

Participant 3 said:

"I can apply it in real life situation and use it in my way of style."

It was found that from their struggles with different strategies, students can apply it in real-life situations in their version.

Participant 4 mentioned that,

"Hibaw on sa teachers nga tanan makasabot, walay mabehind sa klase then tarungon sad nla og tudlo. Then keep pushing, padayon lang bisag lisod, niya mangita tag paagi." (Teachers must know that everyone did understand, no one will leave behind in the class then they will teach very well. Then keep pushing, keep moving even if it's difficult and find a way.)

Participant Four (4) suggests that teachers should evaluate the level of understanding of the learners and their process of teaching that pushes everyone to pursue despite unexpected negative possibilities.

Participant 5 stated that,

“Not necessarily nga ihungit sa mga students, since college naman ta, naa tay responsibility nga atong kat unon but then iconsider nilq ang tanang students kay lahilahi man tag styles sa pagkat on. Need nga ilar assess ang students nakat on ba or wala.. Iaccept nalang siya, Move forward lang ghaon sa paglearn niya. Although complex siya nga imong idown imong kaugalingon. Mopush forward ka, mangita kag other opportunity nga mas makallearn better and do better sa imong self. “ (Not necessary that the teachers will spoon-feed the students, since we're already college we have a responsibility to learn it in our own but then they should consider the students because every students have different styles to learn. They need to assess the students if they learn something. Move forward, although it's complex that you will down yourself. Move forward, find other opportunity to learn better and do better with yourself.)

It was found out by Participant 5, that it is not necessary to spoon-feed all the topics, since as a learner it is a responsibility to read and study with the subject regardless of the levels of intelligence, but consideration of the teacher is also in need. Moreover, assessment is helpful to consolidate the learnings of the students and instead of drowning with negativity looking for other alternatives to learn is best for students to acquire.

Participant 4 explained that,

“Mangayo'g tabang sa classmates, magpatudlo nila then sa youtube pod.” (I seek help to my classmates to teach me or go to youtube.)

According to Participant 4, seeking help from their classmate and watching tutorial videos from YouTube is quite helpful to them.

Participant 2 said that,

“Embrace the challenges and bahala nata unsaon pag cope up. Then make a hobby aron malingaw dayon shot ginagmay.” (Embrace the challenges and it's up to us how we cope up. Then make a hobby to have fun.)

The researchers found out that participant 2 suggested that embracing challenges and making them as a hobby is a way better to ease the pain even in just a short span of time.

Participant 3 also said:

“Just love math”

Participant 3 suggested that learning to love the subject is the best way to escape from stress and burden.

Participant 8 explained that,

“Kanang suggestions kay kung sa para sa student's kay kanang bisag dili nimu love ang subject kay kat-onon nalang jud nimu kay kadugyan kay makakuan man kag, “ah! nindut diay ne kay magamit. Magamit ra ne natu sa future or sa kanang daily lives natu te. Nya kung mag embrace ta sa mathematics kay kanang hunahunaon lang jud nimu nga kanang ganahan ka sa subject bisan dili jud gyud niya kanang makallearn ra ka ug kuan niya love niya kadugayan.” (Even if you don't love the subject, we must learn it because as time passes by you will realize that it's nice. Then we can use it in the future endeavor or in our daily lives. If you embraced mathematics, though you don't like it you must love it. And as time pass by you see yourself loving math.)

Suggestions found from participants eight (8) that learning to love the subject is the best way to cope with the pain unexpectedly felt and have a positive outlook about the subjects' usage in everyday life.

Participant 10 mentioned that,

“Ahm akong suggestion kay mag naning ra gud niya kanang avoid procrastination ra gyud mao ra gyud te unya para ma ease ang pain sa mathematics mudawat nalang jud ko nga mudawat nalang jud ko anang mathematics.” (Be studious in your studies avoid procrastination and accept the pain, that's the only way to ease the pain in mathematics.)

The researchers found out that participant ten (10) preferred the suggestion of managing all the unlikeable feelings they felt and just avoiding procrastination so that to ease the pain of mathematics they just really accept the reality of the subject.

The optimistic theme emphasized the positive outlook of the mathematics students amidst the challenges they are facing upon taking the course. They have managed to ease the pain they are feeling through accepting and embracing these challenges. They have also managed to find coping mechanisms like taking a rest and having hobbies.

The Self-directed

Different unbearable pains are present that people might encounter especially in learning Mathematics. Despite these hindrances, there are still people who can manage and look for initiatives to overcome these hindrances along their learning process. Being able to find solutions in their way, and utilizing the use of different social media platforms for educational purposes are one of those strategies they hold to overcome their problem. Moreover, despite their procrastination and negative vices they still dare to seek ways that will feed them with information and learnings that apply to their needs. This can be further discussed by the words of the participants. The way

students foresee the significance of mathematics lies in how they foster their way of learning in a creative, critical, and simple way. This exactly shifts their perception of the traditional role of a teacher into the idea of a teacher who now becomes a mentor who only guides in the learning process for the students to be able to construct and acquire knowledge of mathematics subject (Bishara, 2021).

Participant 8 said that,

“Kanang magkuan nga bisag di ko ganahan nga mosolve kay pugson naku akong kaugalingon niya anadon naku akong kaugalingon nga dapat jud naku ning kat-onon. Ing-anan. Unya kanang ug nay free time, kay magsolve ko ug mga problems kunohay.” (Even though I don’t like to solve, I just force myself, and get used to it that I must need to learn it. In my free time I pretended as if I am solving a problem.)

According to Participant 8, having the ability to push through despite negative instinct and influence is what drives them most, and using their free time to learn independently by solving math-related problems.

Participant 9 explained that,

“Kuan kanang magbasa maning kamot basa, sabton.” (Read, re-read and understand.)

According to Participant 9, reading in advance to understand the topic is better to understand well the topic.

Participant 2 stated that,

“Maghimo nalang ko ug akoang strategy kay gidawat raman nako ang nga strategies sa teacher.” (I make my own strategies as I accepted the way how the teacher uses his/her strategy in teaching.)

According to Participant 2, they make their own strategies to cope with the subject.

Participant 4 mentioned that,

“Mangayo'g tabang sa classmates, magpatudlo nila then sa youtube podt.” (I seek help to my classmates to teach me or go to YouTube.)

According to Participant 4, seeking help from their classmate and watching tutorial videos from YouTube is quite helpful to them.

Participant 5 said that,

“Isearch sa youtube, din makat on nka ana” (I search in YouTube, in that way I learn it.)

Participant 5 finds that YouTube is really helpful for them to understand well the lesson.

Participant 6 explained that,

“Kuan mangayo ug tabang sa classmates, magpatudlo nalang nila or sa youtube. Unya mao ra na.” (I seek help to my classmates to teach me or in youtube, that’s all.)

Participant 6 found it quite easy to understand with the help of their classmate and watched some tutorial videos from YouTube.

Participant 7 mentioned that,

“So, in what way, kay kuan since expected naman jod kay since pag highschool namo kay, expected jd na nga bisan simple ra ilahang mga examples nga gihatag naa jd na sa ilang exams nga complex ang problems so before sa ilang exams like kanang mga finals gani lamang major exams kay I did my best nga mag-study jod para inig kuan na, answer na, is naa jod moy idea and then maka-answer jod mo though limited ang time nilang gihatag.” (I just expect it like in my previous high school, the teacher uses simple example, and during the term exam they give complex problems, especially major subject so before the exam I did my best, to study, for me to have a knowledge and I can answer the exam in the given time frame.)

The researchers found out from participant 7, that it is expected for them to have simple problems during discussions yet complex problems during term examination. It drives them to be prepared and well-equipped to answer the examination.

Participant 10 stated that,

“Kanang kuan nalang mag self-learning nalang kanang kung wala ko kasabot an ang kay mag search nalang ko sa youtube unga mao rana te unga mangutana pud ko sa ako uban classmate.” (Self-learning and if I cannot understand, I search it in Youtube. And I also ask my classmates.)

The researcher found out from Participant 10, that self-study is a way better to understand the topic than watching tutorials from YouTube.

Participant 4 also stated that,

“Makat on nga dili nalang mo rely sa teachers. Maresourceful ko, moadto nlang ug YouTube, mga videos. “ (I learned how to not rely on my teachers. I have become resourceful, like watching YouTube videos.)

The researchers found out that students become independent and resourceful as they initiate to watch video lessons from Youtube in order to cater their struggles in understanding the lesson.

Participant 5 explained that,

“Although nagkastruggles sa mga strategies nga gitudlo, izearch nila sa YouTube. Din through this, makat on nag another strategies, steps and knowledge nga wala sa teacher. Makat on in a lighter way.” (Although, there are struggles in strategies that have been taught, we search it in YouTube. Then through this, we can learn new strategies, steps and knowledge that is not being taught by the teacher. We can learn in a lighter way.)

It was found out that students initiated to watch video lessons from YouTube as they were having trouble understanding the lessons being taught by their teachers in using different strategies. It is much lighter for the students and it makes them become knowledgeable as they were able to learn something from what they watched which is also not being taught by their teacher.

Participant 6 mentioned that,

“Kuan, makat-on ko nga murag dili nalang mo-rely sa kung unsay kuan sa maestro ba, mangita ko ug akoang pamaagi, kanang resourcefulness. Ma resourceful ko nga moadto nalang ko sa youtube motan-aw ug mga video aron makat-on ko. Mao na.” (You will learn not to rely on what has been taught by the teacher. I would find a way and that made me become resourceful. I became resourceful in a way that I would open YouTube and watch videos so that I can understand the lesson.)

It was found out that students become independent with their learnings as they don't rely with their teachers but instead, they look for other ways as to learn more like watching video lessons from Youtube.

Participant 7 stated that,

“So nachallenge jod, nindot kaayo siya kay ma-challenge gani siya ug huna-huna nga dapat imoha jong mo explore pa jd ka, mo expound pa jod ka, mo go pa jod ka sa imong own research para mas masabtan ang ilahang gi-discuss not just nga mag-kuan ka maghuwat nga hungitan sa ilang gi-discuss.” (I am very challenged. It is nice because it will challenge my mind and made me explore things, to expound more about what you have researched. In that way I can understand what they have discussed not just waiting to be spoon-fed by their discussion.)

It is said that students explore in their own learning like having research to expound and to have a better understanding with the topic. It's about being initiative as they don't wait their teachers spoon feed them.

Participant 8 said that,

“Kanang kuan kanang ganahan nakug ayg kanang kuanon naku akong time nga karun ganahan ko mo kanang ganahan ko mo learn run ug math kay magtuon ko run niya kanang dili sad pwedi ra naku undangan gane te kay naa raman sa google classroom.” (I will give time for studying and learning math. I will study one moment and I can also leave it anytime because it was just posted in the google classroom.)

The researchers found out from participant 8, that they want to depend on learning mathematics from their own will as they may have the courage to study well in their own time pace as every lesson are accessible in google classroom.

Participant 6 said:

“Kinahanglan nga ang mga teacher's kay kuanon pod nila ba nga dili mabiyaan ang uban or matanong nila ug kanang tudlo. Kanang keep pushing, mo kuan lang gyud ka mgpadayon bisag lisod, imoha na jod mga ipadayon, mangita ug paagi.” (Teacher should ensure that no one will get behind with their discussion, before proceeding to the next topic. Just jeep pushing, keep going though it's hard. It's up to us to find ways of coping it.)

Participant 6 suggested that teachers should inspire learners to continue and have the goal to uplift all the learners and make sure that no one is left behind.

Participant 7 mentioned that,

“So, for me ang suggestion nako is that maybe ilahang kuan tas-an ang time nga ikuan per lesson. Nga ilang kuan lang maghatag sila ug exam kay kanang saktong ang time dili jod dali-dalion and then how I will ease kay kuan I will listen sa ilang discussion and then syempre magtuon and then i-apply sad ang ilahang...akong mga nakat-onan gikan nila.” (So, for me, my suggestion is that they should increase the time spent per lesson. And during exam teacher must give students a longer time to answer. And then how I eased the pain, is that I'll listen to their discussion and then of course study and apply it.)

It was found out from participant seven (7) that providing enough time for the discussion proper is in depth need in order to be catch up well, specifically during examination.

Participant 9 explained that,

“Kuan kanang keep working hard kanang do everything that is supposed to be done. Dili mag procrastinate unya kuan time management and niya kuan magbasa jud permi. cope up nalang jud wala namay kuan Wala juy namay laing kuan kanang way. imo ramang adjust ikaw ramuy adjust.”

It was found out from participant 9, that positive attitudes must be apply and avoid procrastination in order to finished everything, having time management and adjustment will at some point give them the opportunities to cope up everything.

Participant 9 also mentioned that,

“Kuan kanang mas maka kat. on ko ug kuan kanang maminaw ug tarong gani kay para kausang sulti nila makuha dayon nako. kanang akong paningkamotan na ing. Ana kanang mauna na murag mag porsigido ko nga maminaw jud taman kay dili naman said mabalik kay mo proceed na ug lain. Focus ra ang akong advantage sa uban.” (Just keep working hard and do everything that was supposed to be done. Don't procrastinate, manage your time and always read. Just cope with it and you need to be flexible in order to adjust to it.)

It was found out from participant 9, that they can grasp the lesson easily when they focused on the discussion in order to continue to the next discussion, as it can encourage them listen and learn in a one pace of time.

The Self-Directed theme emphasized the active and positive response of the students to look for alternatives to improve their ability in internalizing the lessons without just relying to their teachers. They also consider other platforms such as YouTube that contains tutorial videos that relates to math lessons. With this, they can prepare their selves during examinations through studying.

The Discomfort

Many students experiencing discomfort due to some complexity of the topic and the utilization of the teaching strategies. Together with the influences brought by their classmates which drag them along with their confusion towards the subject. With these, students conceal hurtful feelings within themselves that result to loss of interest towards the subject. In addition, it makes them feel pressured and stressed. Notably, the loss of interest of the learners in mathematics subject is due to the weak foundation of mathematics in the prior years of learning, this further stipulate the different pain and problems among the students in learning mathematics (Nazari, 2021).

As Participant 8 said:

“Kuan kay pag-online te, kay walay signal tarong sa amo gani. Unya enig klase ni sir kay putol-putol ang tingog ug kanang maka ug ma di ko makapaminaw bisan gamay kaayu ang isulti ni sir kay murag mawala ko sa akong concentration ug mao to dili na ko makasabot sa sunod. Kanang magpost siya sa kanang google classroom namo, pero kanang mas nindut jud tong e-explain gani ug tarung kay kung sa ihatag ra nila sa kanang topic nga kanang shortcut kaayu te niya mao to. Sa face-to-face kay ang kuan lang ang kuang lang jud sa face-to-face te kay daghang kanang ang sa class. For example sa classmate gane, saba kaayo ing-ana nya ,dili ka kafocus ug tarung pero ok ra man ang the rest. Kato lang jud mga nang saba ing-ana.” (In online learning, the internet connection is so weak that when our teacher will have our discussion, he lagged. And when I can't listen to what he said, my concentration will be fazed and I can't understand the next topic because of that. He would post on our google classroom but it would be better if he explained it thoroughly because if he would just give the topics in shortcut then... In face to face, there are lot of us. For example, our classmates are loud that is why I cannot focus but the rest are okay. Just the loud noise.)

The researchers found out that during online class, students are having trouble with their internet connection that even in little time that they were not able to join google meet, it led them out of concentration in understanding the lesson. Posting lessons in google classroom with proper discussion is much better for the student's understanding unlike posting only. While during face-to-face classes, the nuisance from the peers is a challenge also to the students as it affects their concentration in listening.

Participant 10 stated that,

“Kato jud pag online class kanang permi jud me nag struggle jud me ato man to nag meet namo si sir loading bading me unya na siyay lain gi mention nga topic unga naq dayon siya sa bag.o nasad mabiyaan me. mabiyaan me. Unya karon ma na Aga face-to-fac Kay wala ra man sad kay nindot raman sad mutudlo Si sir namo ung a kuan rapud ciya namo.” (During the online class, we are struggling especially with our internet connection. When we are having an online meeting with our professor, we're being left behind with the new topics because of our slow internet connection. However, now that we have a face-to-face class, we are no longer having any trouble because our teacher discusses the topics very well.)

The researcher found out from participant 10, that they struggle more during the height of online class due to their poor internet connection, but during these face-to-face classes it seem very light to them as they prefer the strategies used by their professor.

Participant 9 stated that,

“Ahh kuan kanang nausab na ron kay sauna magtudlo ug math is everyday jud karun kay na asynchronous and synchronous na ang type. So, moadjust pa mi kay syempre first year sad. So kuan, maglisud. As of now, mag adjust pa mi sa kuan nga sa college kay imuha na jud own paningkamot. So far, ok ra man modiscuss kanang kuan ah ang challenges Lang usahay is kanang dili mapaminaw gani kanang questions kung naa kay personal nga pangutana kay magdali kay taas ang coverage gani kanang muana, imbes mangutana ka kay ikaw nalang jud maningkamot ug sabot. Mo proceed nalang sa lain nga topic kay taas ang coverage dapat human na sya nga kuan

kay sa sunod lain napud.” (It was now different because before, teaching math is everyday but now it became asynchronous and synchronous type (of class). We are also in our adjustment since we are still in first year. So, we are struggling. As of now, we still adjusting in college because we are on our own. So far, the discussion is okay but the challenges sometimes are when we can’t voice out our personal questions because we are in a hurry due to long coverage. Instead of asking, I try to understand it on my own. We proceeded to the different topic because of the long coverage and that it should be done because there is another one.)

The researchers found out from participants 9 that there is a change in teaching math subject wherein there is synchronous and asynchronous type. As a freshman student, adjustment is really a must to cope up with the new ways. Moreover, it is fine when it comes to discussion but the only problem is that when it comes to internet connection, that I sometimes hesitate to ask question in order minimize the time in the discussion, instead of depending I just find my ways to study.

Participant 10 also stated that,

“Katong online kay katong loading unya mahadlok sad me mo ask questions ni sir ato kay basin unyag ni answer na ciya unya loading me. Karon mga Face-to face wala raman sad kay nindot raman mutudlo si sir namo. kay usahay dugay niya online pa ang uban” (When we have our online class, the internet connection is weak and then we are afraid to ask questions to our teacher thinking maybe he already mentioned it. Now in face-to-face, there is none so far, our teacher discusses efficiently. Sometimes it is too long and some are still held online.)

It was found out that during online class the problem is the internet connection that it led the students hesitant to ask questions to the teacher as they might missed the moment that the teacher already explained. While during face-to-face classes, the competency of a teacher really matters as it can lead to no problem with the students.

Participant 1 mentioned that,

“Stress, samot ng makakuha ka og lowest score, then pressure pa judt asta ang parents.” (Stressful especially if I got lowest score, and pressured by my parents.)

It was found out by participant 1, that they felt the stress that often triggered when they got the lowest score and the pressure from parents.

Participant 3 explained that,

“It makes me sleep late at night to cope up the discussions.”

It was found out from participants 3 that it made them slept late at night thinking how to cope up with the discussion. This is really happening as also reflected by freshmen students in the university (Distor et al., 2022).

Participant 5 stated that,

“Ganahan kang makat on din confident na kaayo unta ka mosolve but sa exam kay complex naman, ma low imong confidence din maconfuse ka unsaon pag answer then makahunahuna ka nga mao ba ni among topic? Mora mag wala sa topic.” (You want to learn more and you will be more confident in answering the exam but the given questions are complex. Your confidence will be affected and became confused on how to answer. You will think that is this on the topic? I think this is not on the topic.)

It was found out from participant 5 that they really want to learn and even got the confidence to solve problem after the discussion yet, when it comes to the term examination, they felt the loss of their confidence as the topic becomes complex which made them doubt about their answer, and questioned if they have been encounter the problem being asked.

Participant 6 mentioned that,

“Makadepress, makawala siya ug gana ug maka-apekto pod sa imong self-esteem. Dili man kaya nako ang math uy. Ganahan ka nga mo shift nalang kay ma-apektuhan imong competence ba, imong confidence. Murag dili na nuon ka mosamot na nuon imong dili kabalo.” (It causes depression and loss of self-esteem. It also drives me to tell myself that I can’t handle math and leads me to think to shift to another course because it can affect my competence and confidence. It also causes me to the extent to dwell my thought that I can really handle math.)

The researchers found out from participant 6, that it is depressing which cause the loss of their interest and as well as their self-esteem which at the same time drives them to think that they cannot handle math well and think to shift into another course.

Participant 7 said:

“Sometimes kung masobrahan na gani kaayo ilang paghatag ug mga kuan, mga activities or mga complex problems maglisod jod mi like, sakit jod kaayo huna-hunaan sa huna-huna gani so, after that naa say kuanon nga dili ra namo kaya, maka-ana mi then tungod pod goro ma sa among pagprocrastinate ngs maka-ana mi. Then kuan, pero so far kaya ra man pod siya kung magpositive lang jod ta sa huna-huna.” (Sometimes if they give us too much activities or complex problems, we struggled. It affects my brain too much. If there are some activities that we can’t bear, we will think that maybe it is also because of our procrastination, we say. So far, everything is

bearable if you just think positive.)

It was found out from participant 7, that too much activities and complex problems thrown to them lead them to suffer headache but still there are some also they can deal with. They also think that maybe it is due to their procrastination which made them feel uncomfortable feeling, but so far if they think in a positive way, they think they can handle it in any way.

Participant 10 explained that,

“Kato jud pag online class kanang permi jud me nag struggle jud me ato man to nag meet namo si sir loading bading me unya na siyay lain gi mention nga topic unga naq dayon siya sa bag.o nasad mabiyaan me. mabiyaan me. Unya karon ma na Aga face-to-fac Kay wala ra man sad kay nindot raman sad mutudlo Si sir namo ung a kuan rapud ciya namo.” (During the online class, we are struggling especially with our internet connection. When we are having an online meeting with our professor, we’re being left behind with the new topics because of our slow internet connection. However, now that we have a face-to-face class, we are no longer having any trouble because our teacher discusses the topics very well.)

The researcher found out from participant 10, that they struggle more during the height of online class due to their poor internet connection, but during these face-to-face classes it seem very light to them as they prefer the strategies used by their professor.

The Discomfort theme emphasized the struggles and pain that the students experienced during the asynchronous and synchronous classes. They have experienced losing their focus because of the poor internet connection. They also struggled during meetings because they are hesitant in asking questions for them to comprehend the discussion, clearly. Moreover, during synchronous classes the same discomfort has been experienced due to the noises that their classmates created. Furthermore, these students also experienced stress, pressure, depression, loss of confidence and self-esteem, headache, and sleepless nights in learning math subjects.

The Teachers’ Criticizer

Students merely point out teachers lapses in considering their level of understanding in the lesson. These instances lead them to procrastinate more and dwell into unlikable vices that made them drive to feel frustration. Students even refer them as a pain in the head due to their complex task that sometimes it triggers students fear, doubt and stress toward the subject. Moreover, instead of accepting the teacher’s way of teaching, students consider those as a burden and hassle especially when their strategies are not applicable for all the learners and thus, their hidden queries and confusion is not heard. This can be further discussed by the words of the participants.

Participant 1 mentioned that,

“Based on teaching di judt masabtan. In terms sa exam samot di kasabot kay isituational man. “ (Based on their (teacher) teaching, I still have difficulty learning it. In terms of exam, I also have confusion because some of it are situational.)

According to participant 1, situational exam in Mathematics is much harder to understand which researchers found out that students prefer exam which is not more on situational.

Participant 2 stated that,

“Naglibog tungod sa kadaghang strategies ug tungod ana, dili na makakat on.” (Confused because there are lot of strategies and because of that I cannot learn.)

The researchers found out that utilizing different strategies in teaching Mathematics can cause confusion to the students which also resulted in difficulty to learn as their minds might also be stirred up.

Participant 3 mentioned that,

“Topics are broad and teachers doesn't explain it very well.”

Teachers are the givers of knowledge, hence the way they teach also matters. It was found out that due to the insufficient explanation of the teachers, it resulted pain to the students to understand as topics are also broad that it really needs specific supporting discussions.

Participant 4 explained that,

“Paspas kaayo ilang pagdiscuss then nig pangutana "kasabot class" naay duha nga moingon, oo kasabot maam. Mo proceed na dayun sa next. Then dili na nila maexplain pag ayo ang basic, modretso nas complex maong malisdan na ang students. (Mabyaan na, di na mapadayun).” (Their (teacher) discussions are fast and when they asked if the class understood, there are two or more that would say “yes”. Then the teacher would proceed to the next topic. They will not explain the basics thoroughly and would directly tackle complex (problems) that is why students have a hard time. (Topic) was left behind and unfinished.)

The researchers found out that during class discussions, there are students who can easily learn with the topic but there are silent students that sometimes even if they have confusion regarding with the lesson, they remain silent for their teachers teach like always in a hurry. And with this scenario, it resulted to student’s difficulty to understand complex lessons for the basic lessons were not being

emphasized.

Participant 5 stated that,

“Simple examples din nigr test na macomplex og out of the box na sa topic. Then dili nila ispecificy ang mga steps on solving that equation. Naa naman sa ilang (teachers) mind nga dli na angayng hungitan ang students kay lagi naagian na sa pag lower grades so need nga irefresh ang students.” (Examples given are simple but when it comes to exam, complex problems are given. The topics also are out of the box. Then they (teachers) did not specify the steps on solving the equation. They thought that there is no need to spoon-feed the topics to the students because we already encounter the topics in the lower grades so we just need to refresh it.)

It was found out that due to the reason that the lessons were being tackled during previous years, teachers believe that there’s no need to discuss it deeper. By that, students were not ready to solve as it is not guaranteed that they remember every steps in solving equation. Thus, students are experiencing difficulty in answering as the test were so out of the box for only simple examples are given but complex problems are given during exam.

Participant 6 mentioned that,

“Paspas may solve sila dili na kaapas. Unya naay mangutana nga nakasabot na mo? Naay uban nga moingon, o, unya ang uban kay wala kasabot. Mo proceed na gani sila. Kuan pod, dili kuanon ang basic, mo diretso sila sa lisod unya mabiyaan ang uban, dili na kapadayon.” (They solve (equation) very fast and the students can’t follow. Then they would ask if we understood, some would say “yes”, even though some of us did not. They will proceed to other topics. They would directly tackle difficult (topics) without start at the basic, then the others would be left behind.)

It was found out that there are two kinds of students based on their level of understanding, the fast learners and the slow learners, but both are eager to learn. It’s just a matter of time that most students need more time in order to finally understand the lesson. But due to time constraints, they left with no choice but to proceed with the next lesson having a hard time understanding the basic lesson.

Participant 7 said:

“For me ang mga challenges, there are a lot o challenged as students. So kung sa mga math teacher namo ang basehan kay kuan in delivering their lessons kay naay uban nga magdiscuss and then they will give examples from... First examples nila kay mga simple examples then some teachers kay maghatag ug complex examples amd then they.. ang mga challenges nga maface ana kay sometimes inig hatag nila ug mga exam or test is that naay part nga sayon ra namo mgs maansweran pero naa say part nga kana ganing complex na kaayo siya and then sometimes tungod sa time constraints sad sa time nga ilang ihatag kasy... masabot ra man pod goro tong complex nilang question nga gihatag nila pero tungod sa time nga limited kaayo is murag magdali-dali mi amd then dili na namo ma-analyze ug tarong ang ilang questions amd that results nga ma-wrong sa among answers but inig find out namo sa inig solution na or sa ilang answers kay... ana-on ra diay to siya, so mao to siya.” (There are lot of challenges faced by the students when it comes to math, the teacher’s way of delivering the lessons is through discussion and will give simple examples afterwards. The challenges on it is that sometimes their exams or tests have easy parts that is easy to answer but there are also complex parts that are difficult to answer. Then sometimes it is also because of time constraints. I think the complex questions that they have given can be answered but because of limited time we would hurry and then we can’t analyze the questions properly and that results to our answers to be incorrect. But when we found out after we have saw the solution and to those correct answers, we would realize that, that’s how you to do it.)

It was found out that the way teachers deliver their lessons is a challenge to the students in a way that they gave more on simple examples and few on complex. But the students are capable in solving the problem even though some parts are complex which they also have trouble in solving but they believe that having enough time will allow them to analyze and solve thoroughly of what the problem is all about. It’s just that they don’t have enough time to think deeply which resulted them in getting wrong answer.

Participant 10 also explained that,

“Kanang ang advantage rasad namo kay is mangutana me ni sir mutubag rasad siya unya dili gani me niya biyaan unya mo suggest sad si sir ug uban nga site gani nga amoang ikuan tan.awon unya mo suggest sad siya ug site nga picturan ra gani namo unya i solve unya mao raman iyang kuan namo.” (Our advantage is to ask questions, which our teacher would also answer. He doesn’t want us to be left behind and sometimes he would suggest some sites for us to visit to watch and take picture to solve it.)

The researcher found out from participant 10, that it is their advantage when they asked for clarification from the teacher and received simple answer which can help them understand more the topic, and they even got some suggestion where to site and where to find problems to capture in order for the to practice.

The Teachers’ Criticizer highlighted the different dilemma the students have felt and reacted with the way how the teachers deliver the lesson. Another dilemma for them is the fast pace of their teacher in delivering the lesson wherein they cannot totally catch up the discussion. For some instances, the teachers utilized simple examples during discussion, yet, giving complicated assessment with a limited time duration which is quite not enough for the students to finish their work.

Conclusions

Mathematics is a complex subject where different teaching strategies need to be considered and utilized in order to make it more accessible. Yet, each student has a different level of intellectual capacity; some can learn fast, while others take time to internalize the topic. In line with this, it still brought a different impact to the learners in the way they react, feel, think, and initiate taking action throughout their learning process, where THE PESSIMIST dwells in negative thinking and unlikable vices and they can feel quite at ease. THE OPTIMIST prefers to pursue despite their moments of hardship and even on the verge of giving up. THE SELF-DIRECTED have a strong sense of courage and the will to seek alternatives to fill in their unsatisfied gained knowledge. The discomfort is the unbearable pain experienced by the participants during their learning process and as a result of their efforts. THE TEACHERS' CRITICIZERS are those who considered that their insufficiency in learning was the outcome of the teachers' way of delivering the lessons, but there are still those who appreciate the efforts of their teachers in imparting knowledge. It is recommended to consider the participants' level of intellect when determining how the teacher will deliver the lesson. In addition, asking for and considering the students' feedback during and after the discussion will allow the entire class to achieve smooth learning transitions. It is also important for the students to take their responsibilities seriously and seek other alternatives to meet their learning needs.

References

- Algani, Y. (2019). Innovative Ways to Teach Mathematics: Are they Employed in Schools? *Journal of Computer and Education Research* 7(14), 496-514. <https://doi.org/10.18009/jcer.6121>
- Arthur, Y., Simon, A., Amo-Asante., & Asare, B. (2022). Modeling student's interest in mathematics: Role of history of mathematics, peer-assisted learning, and student's perception. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/12458>
- Atoyebi, O. M. & Atoyebi, S. B. (2022). The Causes of Anxiety in Mathematics Among Private Secondary School Students: A Case Study of Students in Egbedore Local Government, Osun State, Nigeria. *Adeleke University Journal of Science (AUJS)*, 1(2), <https://aujs.adelekeuniversity.edu.ng>
- Bacong, J., Encabo, C. M., Limana, J. M., & Cabello, C. (2023). The High School Students' Struggles and Challenges in Mathematics: A Qualitative Inquiry. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(3), 306-312.
- Bell, E., & Bryman, A. (2007). The ethics of management research: an exploratory content analysis. *British journal of management*, 18(1), 63-77.
- Bishara, S. (2021). The cultivation of self-directed learning in teaching mathematics. *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issue*, 13(1), 82-95.
- Bosch, D. (2022). Factors in the behaviour of mathematics teachers that influence math anxiety amongst high school students.
- Bouck, E. C., Working, C., & Bone, E. (2017). Manipulative Apps to Support Students With Disabilities in Mathematics. *Intervention in School and Clinic*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451217702115>
- Cabello, C. A., Abadiano, M. N., Mabitad, A., Pulma, D. B., & Hipe, A. (2021). Gamification in Education: The Motivation-Exploration-Implementation Theory. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(7).
- Cabello, C., Ancot, R., Cabanog, A. M., & Doble, C. (2023). Expediency in Honing Literacy and Numeracy in the New Normal. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(2), 1-1.
- Cabello, C., Libradilla, C., Derequito, F., & Derequito, D. D. (2023). Fundamental Understanding of Mathematical Problems: Challenges and Breakthroughs. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 12(2), 1-1.
- Cevikbas, M. & Kaiser, G. (2020). Flipped classroom as a reform-oriented approach to teaching mathematics. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 52(7), 1291-1305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-020-01191-5>
- Distor, J. M., Cabello, C., & Tus, J. (2022). Social media usage and sleep quality among freshmen college students in the new normal. *Specialis Ugdymas*, 2(43), 2030-2046.
- Elsayed, A. (2022). The effects of the interaction between the use of the IMPROVE strategy in teaching mathematics and achievement levels on the acquisition of algebraic concepts and habits of mind among tenth grade student in Oman.
- Emia, A. J., Lamosao, R., Lamosao, R., Silagpo, A. M., Cantila, J., Albite, C., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). The Pre-Service Teachers' Uphill Climb in the New Normal: Stories to Tell. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(6), 529-540.
- Enario, J. R., Glinogo, J. F., Salmeron, G., Salmeron, G. M., Ocaña, M., Ocaña, J., ... & Minyamin, A. (2022). Enriching the teaching of the Appropriate Use of Graphic Organizer through Guided Visual-Imagery. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(2), 195-202.

- Fajriah, F. (2017). Learning Journal: Improving Teaching Strategies Through Students' Reflections. *Sukma Journal Pendidikan* 1(2), 301-327. <https://doi.org/10.32533/01204>
- Gabriel, B. C., Nepomuceno, J. D., Kadusale, M. H., Taneo, J. D., & Cabello, C. A. (2022). The Compromised Most Essential Learning Competencies: A Qualitative Inquiry.
- Gordeva, T., Sheldon, K., & Sychev, O. (2019). Linking academic performance to optimistic attributional style: attributions following positive events matter most. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 35, 21-48.
- Hu, B., Li, Y., Zhang, X., & Roberts, S. (2021). The quality of teacher feedback matters: Examining Chinese teachers' use of feedback strategies in preschool math lessons. *Teaching and Teacher Education* 98(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.tate.2020.103253>
- Jamieson, J. P., Black, A. E., Pelaia, L. E., & Reis, H. T. (2021). The impact of mathematics anxiety on stress appraisals, neuroendocrine responses, and academic performance in a community college sample. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 113(6), 1164–1176. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000636>
- Khanal, B., Panthi, R., & Belbase, S. (2021). Mathematics learning strategies of high school students in Nepal. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s4354-021-00165-y>
- Lo, C. K., Hew, K. F., & Chen, G. (2017). Toward a set of design principles for mathematics flipped classroom: A synthesis of research in mathematics education. *Educational Research Review*, 22(1), 50-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2017.08.002>
- Mainali, B. (2021). Representative in Teaching and Learning Mathematics. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics Science and Technology, (IJEMST)*, 9(1), 1- 21. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijemst.1111>
- Mazana, Y. M., Suero, C., & Olifage, C. R. (2019). Investigating Students' Attitude towards Learning Mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14 (1) , 207-231. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/3997>
- Nagro, S. A., Weiss, M. P., & Daley, J. T. (2017). What really works with exceptional learners.
- Nazari, M. (2021). Investigation of Mavlana Aznab Sheberghani School students' reluctance in math subject. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 4(3), 163-167. doi: 10.53894/ijrss.v4i3.72
- Papama, F., Makeleni, S., & Masha, R. (2022). Cooperative Versus Traditional Teaching Strategy in Grade 9 General Education & Training Certificate (GETC) Mathematics. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSRJRME)*, 12(1), 52-60. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-1201055260>
- Popova, A., Evans, D. K., Breeding, Mary. E., & Arancibia, V. (2022). Teacher professional development around the world: The gap between evidence and practice. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 37(1), 107-136. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lkab006>
- Ramirez, G., Shaw, S T., & Maloney, E A. (2018). Math Anxiety: Past Research, Promising Interventions, and a New Interpretation Framework. *Educational psychologist*, 53,(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2018.1447384>
- Schulze, S. & Bosman, A. (2018). Learning style preferences and Mathematics achievement of secondary school learners. *South African Journal of Education*. 39(1). <https://tinyurl.com/2jfyfvfd>.
- Segarino, G. M., Labisig, J., Calmerin, L., & Cabello, C. (2022). SIMS as Intervention in Enriching the Teaching of Fundamental Operations in Mathematics: An Action Research. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 5(1), 11-20.
- Seiter, A. (2019). Why do we hate math and how do we teach it?
- Shin, M., Bryant, D. P., Bryant, B. R., & McKenna, J. W. (2017). Virtual Manipulatives: Tools for Teaching Mathematics to Students With Learning Disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 52(3), 148–153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451216644830>
- Trigueros, R., Padilla, A., Parra, J. M., Lirola, M. J., Luengo, A. V., Perez, Patricia., & Liria, R. (2020). The Influence of Teachers on Motivation and Academic Stress and Their Effect on the Learning Strategies of University Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17239089>
- Whittemore, R., Chase, S. K., & Mandel, C. L. (2001). Validity in qualitative research. *Qualitative health research*, 11(4), 522-537.
- Wu, T. (2020). Changing the teaching method to reduce math anxiety CTL119H (Course essay). Changing the teaching method to reduce math anxiety.
- Zhang, X. (2022). The Role of EFL Teachers' Emotioncy in Preventing Students' Boredom and Pessimism. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.880234>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Maria Junavie E. Quilestino

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Edel Shae E. Atienza

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Anjielyn T. Baguio

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Joyce Ann B. Bornea

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Clear P. Caldusa

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jey Ann M. Cortes

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jevan Rey A. Javierto

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

John Vincent L. Panuan

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Cyril A. Cabello PhD(c)

Cebu Technological University – Philippines